

THE DYNAMICS OF CORONEOLOGISMS

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The article reflects upon the dynamic spread of coroneologisms in all the spheres of the modern world. It aims at focusing on the triggers that urge the language enrichment, on the most active spheres of the use of new words, as well as on the evolutionary dynamics of the complex language system.

The leading impact on the aggressive language enhancement preserves intensive development and use of electronic media and Internet, as well as technology advancement that plays a considerable role. Thus, we shall focus on certain coroneologisms that have been fixed in the language and have become a tool for mass communication.

Cuvinte-cheie: *neologisms, coroneologisms, electronic media, language enhancement*

Introduction

“A snake that cannot cast its skin has to die”, Nietzsche’s words perfectly describe the modern world that fitted in the framework of the coronavirus disease Covid 19 caused by SARS-CoV-2. The present article is aimed at focusing on the dynamics of coroneologisms, words created under the influence of the 21st century pandemic.

The accelerated usage of new media platforms has opened the doors to remote / distance style of living, as the population all around the world had to survive and continue its ongoing routine, that we call life. At the beginning of the 21st century it was challenging for a bigger part of the population to use new media in their everyday life and only digital natives felt like fish in the water. However, the emergence of the pandemic made the humanity quickly adopt to the reality, profiting from what we had, and developing the opportunities provided by the World Wide Web.

The pandemic has generated an abundance of new words and formations, known as coroneologisms, spread in all the spheres of in the human activity, that aim at reflecting the dynamics of the language that is regarded as a living organism. Therefore, the current study is mainly based on new media that is defined by the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary as information and entertainment products and services that use digital technologies such as the internet. [1]

About Coroneologisms

“Coroneologism” is a blending, that was created through simultaneous combination and shortening of the words corona+neologism [2] and it can be defined as neologisms that developed or were created during the COVID-19 pandemic. “Short pieces on coroneologisms have attested to the rise of many new lexical formations, mostly blends. According to Thorne (2020; also cited in CBC, 2020), more than 1,000 new words – both non-specialised and technical terminology – have been created during the current pandemic”, has pointed out A. Roig–Marín. [3]

Digital Information Sources

The digital information sources and publications that have been considered in the present article, have included the following sources, which main criteria of selection was the usage of the English language and availability of its digital form on the internet, covering the main spheres of people's life [4]: The Times, The Guardian, Standard, Glamour Magazine, Daily Mail, Washington Post, Telegraph, Travel Weekly, Women Shealth Mag, Vogue, Better Homes and Gardens, Govtech, Harvard Business Review, Mind Body Online, Travel Pulse, Outlook India, Forbes, Cambridge Independent, The Observer Magazine, BBC, FTADVISER, The Budget Savvy Bride, The Knot, Irish Examiner, Sunday Times, Independent, The Conversation, Citywire, CNBC, NY Post, Hindustan Times, New York Times, Who, New Digital Age, Scotsman, Business Times, Metro, FOX News, Chicago Tribune, Esquire Mag, etc.

Methodology and analysis

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused the outburst in coroneologisms. The present study aims at exploring the new formations, created during the pandemic caused by Covid-19 SARS-CoV-2, through the prism of the Maslow's pyramid of needs [5]. The data were collected from new media. The present study has used the descriptive-qualitative method

of categorizing selected neologisms in accordance to the basic needs described by the scientist.

Maslow pyramid of hierarchy

Therefore, to understand what motivates human beings, Maslow created a pyramid of hierarchy to identify human needs that ranges from concrete needs such as food and water to abstract concepts such as self-fulfillment. Thus, five specified categories of needs are as follows:

- i. *Physiological needs* – refer to basic physical needs that are the most essential like food, clothing, air, water, shelter, sleep, reproduction; people are likely to meet physiological needs first.
- ii. *Safety needs* – based on need for safe and predictable environments and typically react with fear or anxiety when these are not met, these include job, security, resources, health and property.
- iii. *Love and Belonging needs* – focus on feeling loved and accepted, these needs include both romantic relationships as well as ties to friends and family members, sense of connection, need to feel that we belong to a social group.
- iv. *Esteem needs* - involve the desire to feel good about ourselves, respect, self-esteem, status recognition, strength and freedom; therefore, these needs include first of all self-confidence and feeling good about oneself and second of all feeling valued by others; that is, feeling that our achievements and contributions have been recognized by other people.
- v. *Self-Actualization needs* - refers to feeling fulfilled, or feeling that we are living up to our potential, desire to become the most that one can be; however, achieving self-actualization is relatively rare.

Coroneologisms through the prism of Maslow pyramid of hierarchy

Therefore, 131 of coroneologisms were analyzed through the prism of Maslow pyramid of hierarchy and categorized in the following groups:

Physiological needs – *FORO* “fear of running out products”, *HOGO* “hassle of going out: a feeling that leaving the house in order to socialize”, *demi-fine* “jewellery, made from precious metals like gold and silver but not as expensive as fine jewellery”, *broken plan* “a broken plan room, divided into smaller areas for different activities”, *bounceback wardrobe* “all the clothes that someone owns, or wants to buy, for the period of

time after lockdown, when they are back at work and going out socially again”, *microdelivery* “the act of delivering to someone’s house a single item, normally food or drink, very soon after they have ordered it online”, *live shopping noun* “the activity of buying something online from someone who is selling goods or products in real time on a social media platform”, *sleepcast* “a podcast containing sounds and voices that are designed to give you a good night’s sleep”, *proffee* “a drink made by mixing cold coffee with protein powder or with a ready-made drink that contains protein”, *coronasomnia* “the condition of being unable to sleep because of anxiety related to the coronavirus pandemic”, *air curtain* “a flow of air that stays around a single aeroplane passenger and helps to prevent viruses from spreading to other people on the plane”, *community fridge* “a fridge, located in a public space, that is filled with donated food so that people who cannot afford to buy food can take what they need”, *social listening* “the activity of collecting information from social media sites on what people are saying about a particular topic, such as a product or brand”, *lockdown tache* “a moustache that its wearer has allowed to grow during lockdown”, *anti-masker* “someone who refuses to obey the rule that a mask must be worn in public places to help protect people from covid-19”, *coronavision* “problems with eyesight that began or worsened during the period of the covid-19 pandemic and lockdown”, *revenge spending* “the activity of shopping more than usual as a reaction to not having been able or allowed to do so for a period of time”, *social commerce* “the use of social media websites to buy and sell products and services”, *cottagecore* “a lifestyle based on traditional rural activities, or a way of dressing that suggests that lifestyle, usually adopted by people who live in cities”, *anti-fit* “Anti-fit clothes are deliberately designed to fit the wearer’s body very loosely”, *Zoomwear* “a style of dressing that involves wearing clothes suitable for the office above the waist and casual clothing below the waist”, *air bridge* “a flight route between two countries where the covid-19 virus is well controlled, enabling people to travel without having to go into quarantine afterwards”, *collab house* “a large house in which people who work in social media live and work together”.

Safety needs – I. health issues – *posture pandemic* “pain in the shoulders or back, thought to be caused by working at a computer or a gadget or bending down to look at its screen”, *FONO* “fear of normal

life and activities after the restrictions of the Covid-19 pandemic”, *flurona* “a name that describes the condition of being infected with flu and COVID-19 at the same time”, *supercold* “a cold that has more serious symptoms than most colds and is often mistaken for Covid-19”, *vaccine envy* “resentment felt by someone waiting to receive the Covid-19 vaccination”, *immunity debt* “the situation where people have been avoiding exposure to the Covid-19 virus and have therefore not developed immunity to other viruses, causing larger, more serious outbreaks of illness later”, *pingdemic* “the situation where a very large number of people have received an alert on their phone telling them that they must self-isolate as they have been in contact with someone who has Covid-19, causing problems for businesses and services as they cannot go to work”, *vaccine nationalism* “the situation where a country tries to buy supplies of a vaccine before or instead of other, usually poorer, countries”, *social hangover* “a feeling of tiredness and slight illness after meeting and spending time with friends and family, especially after lockdown”, *re-entry anxiety* “a feeling of stress or worry about returning to normal life after the restrictions caused by COVID-19”, *lockdown foot* “a condition resulting from someone having spent lockdown at home in bare feet or slippers, allowing their feet to change shape and making it difficult or painful to wear normal shoes again”, *bungalow leg* “a condition where the leg muscles have become weak through living in a single-storey house and not having to climb stairs”, *headline stress disorder* “a feeling of stress and anxiety caused by reading or watching a lot of negative or worrying news”, *vaccine hunter* “someone who uses the internet to look for and organize covid-19 vaccination appointments on behalf of other people who cannot do this themselves”, *scariant* “any new variant of covid-19 that people are very worried about because of the way it is reported in the media, despite the lack of scientific evidence to suggest it is any more dangerous than the original virus”, *panpanic* “a strong feeling of fear experienced by many people during the covid-19 pandemic, leading to a lack of reasonable thought and action”, *eye yoga* “a type of yoga designed to strengthen the muscles around the eyes”, *above-the-mask* “describes a beauty treatment or product that is used on an area of the face above where a mask is worn, such as the eyes or forehead”, *skin fasting* “the practice of using no, or very few, skincare products on your face for a set period of time, thought by some people to

be good for the skin”, *vaccine stamp* “a mark made in a passport to show that the holder has been vaccinated against the covid-19 virus”, *V-Day* “the day when the vaccination programme against the covid-19 virus was launched in the UK”, *long covid* “a condition in which people who have had the covid-19 virus continue to have symptoms and feel unwell for a long time”, *maskne* “acne caused or made worse by wearing a mask”, *Covid toe* “a rash or red swelling on the toes, thought to be a symptom of the covid-19 virus”, *twindemic* “a widespread outbreak of both flu and covid-19 at the same time”, *digital nutrition* “the process of making sure that using mobile phones, computers etc. is not harmful for your physical and mental health”, *teletherapy* “the treatment of mental illness by discussing someone’s problems with them using videoconferencing rather than in person”, *corona corridor* “an area that people are allowed to travel through to reach a particular destination as the COVID-19 lockdown measures are gradually eased”, *covexit* “the process of easing the restrictions on public life imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic”;

II. employment - *flu hunter* “a scientist who looks for new strains of flu so that an effective vaccine can be developed”, *WFC* “working from cafés”, *clean inboxer* “someone who reads and takes action on every received email”, *DAO* “decentralized autonomous organization: an organisation or company that exists online and is managed according to a set of rules that exist in the form of computer code, with financial transactions being carried out by members using cryptocurrency”, *the Great Resignation* “a trend in the employment market during 2020 and 2021 that has seen a much larger number of people than usual resign from their job”, *returnment* “going back to work after a period of time not in paid employment”, *overemployment* “the practice of a remote worker secretly having more than one full-time job”, *resimercial* “an office with comfortable furniture and design that makes it look more like a room in a home”, *polywork* “the activity of having several different jobs at the same time”, *finfluencer* “someone who attracts followers on social media through giving financial advice”, *flexcation* “a holiday during which parents spend some of the time working from home and children are homeschooled”, *sunshine shift* “a period of time worked by an employee of a café or restaurant that can only open outdoors, and which can be cancelled by the employer if the weather is not good enough to attract customers”, *human cloud* “the freelance workers located anywhere in

the world who are employed to work on individual tasks that can be done on a computer”, *boffice* “a bed used as a workspace by someone who works from home”, *Blursday* “a humorous way of referring to any day of the week in the time of the covid-19 pandemic, from the fact that it is sometimes difficult to know which day it is”, *pub desk* “a table in a pub that someone can use as a desk instead of working at home, usually in return for an hourly or daily payment”, *chronoleadership* “a way of organizing your working hours around the times of day when you naturally feel most awake”, *adaptability quotient* “the ability of someone or the company they work for to adapt to change and stay successful”, *superforecaster* “someone whose job is to predict what certain events or situations are going to be like in the future, and who can do this very accurately”, *collab house* “a large house in which people who work in social media live and work together”, *triple-screen* “to read or watch three screens at the same time”;

III. education – *nanolearning* “a way of learning that involves reading or watching very small pieces of information or other content, usually on the internet”, *goldfish generation* “a way of referring to the group of people who have grown up with smartphones and other technology and have a poor memory and attention span as a result”, *hyflex* “a way of learning in which lessons are given face to face in classrooms and also made available on the internet”, *schoolcation* “a family holiday during which the children receive online schooling”, *flexi-schooling* “the teaching of children partly at home, usually by their parents, and partly at school”, *infodemic* “a very large amount of information that is published about a particular problem, some of which is untrue, therefore making it more difficult to find a solution”, *Zoombombing* “the act of joining a meeting on the Zoom videoconferencing platform without having been invited, with the aim of disrupting it, often by posting inappropriate content”, *triple-screen* “to read or watch three screens at the same time”, *walking around video* “a video posted on a social media platform of someone walking around a particular town or city, designed to give the viewer a virtual tour”, *half-tourist* “someone who travels to a different city or country and spends part of the time working remotely while they are there”, *revenge travel* “the activity of travelling and going on holiday more than usual as a reaction to not having been able or allowed to do so for a period of time”;

IV. economics - *kindness economy* “an economic system that is based on businesses focusing less on profit and more on the interests and values of their customers, employees and society in general”, *shecession* “an economic recession that affects mostly women”, *mortgage prisoner* “someone who is unable to transfer their mortgage to a lender that offers lower interest rates because the rules for borrowing have become stricter or their house is worth less than they owe”, *social commerce* “the use of social media websites to buy and sell products and services”, *revenge spending* “the activity of shopping more than usual as a reaction to not having been able or allowed to do so for a period of time”, *spendemic* “a sudden tendency for people to spend money, usually on unnecessary things”, *phygital* “using a combination of physical and digital elements to sell and market a product”;

V. technology - *screenome* “detailed record of someone’s activity on smartphone”, *affective AI* “a type of artificial intelligence that allows computers to share some of the qualities of the human mind, such as the ability to understand language and solve problems, that can measure and interpret human emotions”, *digital republic* “a country whose citizens can access almost all government services on the internet”, *fearware* “a type of cyber attack that exploits an existing sense of fear among people and encourages them to click on a link that will harm their computer”.

Love and Belonging needs –*vitamin S* “social contact with other people, considered to be as good for your health as the vitamins in food”, *social biome* “the system of relationships and interactions you have with other people, thought to be necessary for good mental and physical wellbeing”, *metaverse* “a shared online space where people, represented by avatars, can take part in many different activities, using virtual reality and augmented reality technology”, *glitch* “a dance, made popular on TikTok, where the dancer moves in a fast, jerky way that makes it look as though the viewer has a bad internet connection”, *cloffice* “a closet that has been turned into a small office space”, *virtual commute* “a way for people who work from home to separate their working hours from their personal time more easily”, *work from anywhere* “the activity of working remotely from any location, not necessarily at home”, *social recession* “a period when there is very little contact between all the people in a society”, *minimony* “a small wedding ceremony that is held instead of, or before, a bigger celebration”, *microwedding* “a wedding to which

only a small number of guests are invited”, *digital campfire* “a small group of people who communicate online, usually on a social media site”, *quaranteam* “a group of people who go into quarantine together”, *lockstalgia* “a feeling of nostalgia for the lockdown period of the covid-19 pandemic”, *skin hunger* “the basic human need to be touched”, *double bubble* “the people from two separate households who are allowed to see each other as part of the gradual easing of restrictions during the covid-19 pandemic”, *coronial* “someone who was born around the time of the covid-19 pandemic”, *quaranteen* “a teenager in the time of the covid-19 lockdown”, *social bubble* “a small group of family and friends who are permitted to see each other as the COVID-19 lockdown measures are gradually eased”.

Esteem needs and *Self-Actualization needs* being on the top of the pyramid of hierarchy are most challenging, request desire to feel good about ourselves, respect, self-esteem, status recognition, strength and freedom, the fulfillment of the human potential and are the hardest to achieve. These categories I would attribute to medicine, and every person that has contributed to fighting with SARS-COV-19, as his/her contribution is deeply appreciate by the whole world, their commitment and endurance to challenges of the pandemic. Therefore, the coroneologisms in these two categories are very few, but they deserve to be included here: *probiotic architecture* “practice of designing and making buildings that can host certain types of bacteria that help keep people healthy”, *Vaxi Taxi* “a taxi that picks people up from their home and takes them to a clinic for their Covid-19 vaccination, with the person sometimes being vaccinated while they are sitting in the taxi”, *medfluencer* “a medical doctor who gives advice, recommends products etc. on social media”.

Conclusions

Various social layers have been deprived of the opportunity to carry out favorite activities, therefore, experience self-esteem, and reaching self-actualization. During the lockdown, word of the year 2020, according to Oxford Dictionary, everyone was offered an unlimited amount of time on television, social networks, being considerably influenced through “information diet” that is known to be mainly destructive if not qualitatively used and meanwhile, generating an abundance of coroneologisms. If we look at the situation from the point of view of the

pyramid Maslow, we will see big losses at the third and fourth levels - socialization and recognition for many, except, medical workers. Upper three “floors” - creativity, aesthetics and spiritual needs - are now turned inward, on the neighbors or on those people and forms of realization that are available through networking. Suddenly the society has been thrown back to the need for security and physiological needs. However, the wave tendency of shifting the picture of the world though different socio-economic-linguistic triggers is as old as the world.

The results of the study are predictable, as issues make people think first of all about their basic necessities to satisfy *physiological* and *security needs*, to physically survive during the pandemic caused by SARS-COV-19. The corpus-based study has identified that out of 131 of coroneologisms, 23 of new formations or around 18 percent of the words analyzed through the prism of the pyramid of hierarchy belong to human needs that highlight concrete necessities such as food and water first of all, however security needs are much more important during the pandemic, identifying 87 neologisms or about 66 percent of coroneologisms. The loss of safe and predictable environments, fear and anxiety, generated new words to face provocation successfully. The presence of 18 coroneologisms or around 13.7 percent in the third category of needs, *Love and Belonging needs*, that refer to feelings, family ties, friends, conclude that it is possible to stay still and pass all the difficulties having close social connections, as we are society-based species. *Esteem needs* and *Self-Actualization needs*, having 2.3 percent or 3 out of 131 of coroneologisms, the top of the pyramid, feeling of being fulfilled, I would like to attribute to the medical staff, as they should have the feeling that they have lived up to their potential, they have become the most that one can be, achieving self-actualization, the diamonds in the Maslow pyramid of hierarchy.

The practice has shown that only the openness and readiness to change is the key mechanism that has helped the humanity to survive, as Nietzsche’s words perfectly describe the modern world that fitted in the framework of the coronavirus disease Covid 19 caused by SARS-CoV-2 “A snake that cannot cast its skin has to die”.

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